

Reproducibility study:

One Chatbot Per Person: Creating Personalized Chatbots based on Implicit User Profiles

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Group 35

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Our aim is to reproduce the study PChatbot, a large Chinese dialogue dataset collected from Weibo and Judicial forums, that has undergone processes such as anonymization, deduplication, segmentation, and filtering for use in data-driven dialogue systems. Unlike existing datasets, PChatbot includes anonymized user IDs and timestamps to allow for personalized dialogue model development. The dataset is larger than existing Chinese datasets and has been tested using several state-of-the-art dialogue models.

1 Introduction

Nowadays the topic of Chatbots is omnipresent as for example ChatGPT is a current trend. In this paper we want to examine the paper “One Chatbot Per Person: Creating Personalized Chatbots based on Implicit User Profiles” which proposes a method to make chatbots user-alike. To personalize a chatbot different aspects should be achieved like user-data-collection, input-analyzation, custom user experience improving via

preference-actualisation which can be reached by continuously monitoring the user-chat-history.

In order to get a first impression on the chosen paper's level of reproducibility (aside from other criteria) we were using the PRIMAD-Model to identify critical aspects, which are needed to reproduce the experiments of the paper. These are outlined in short now and are examined in detail in the corresponding chapters of the paper.

Platform: Some Code of the paper was published in a GitHub-Repository

Research Objectives: Creating personalized chatbots according to historical user profiles (data)

Implementation: Python Code and some scripts

Methods: DHAP (learning user profiles from Dialogue History Automatically for Personalized chatbots) – model developed by the research team with different components using different approaches to generate personalized chats

Actors: Users who use the Chatbot-Solution, if they are busy and send generated chat-answers in their own user-style

Data: Labeled chat-history data from the PChatbot-Dataset

2 Methods

The model DHAP used in the original paper consist of four components:

- history encoder
- personalized post encoder
- user history memory
- personalized decoder

Each of the above listed components is based on different common models, which are listed below (in the same order as the component-list):

- Transformer
- Bidirectional GRU which is initialized by a general user profile to make it user-aware
- key-value memory which records n historical post response pairs $H=((P_1,R_1), \dots, (P_n, R_n))$
 - where these responses are used to generate dynamic post-aware user profiles

- the from above generated profiles are fused and based on CopyNet the proposed model builds the answer by generating words with as well a generic vocabulary and the personalized user vocabulary (taken from the generated profile)

In the paper there are the following formulas in use, in order to generate respective posts: In order to generate the personalized responses Y (generated words y_1, \dots, y_{t-1} according to the probabilities of the corresponding vocabularies) the following formula is applied in dependence of the User-posts X and the corresponding user-history H . For the probability of generation DHAP is used.

$$p(Y|X, u) = p(Y|X, H) = \prod_{t=1}^{L_Y} p(y_t|y_{<t}, X, H)$$

To get a better insight on the whole DHAP-model the structural overview of it's procedure is depicted below (which is provided in the original paper [1])

Figure 1: DHAP overall model-structure [1]

Furthermore in order to avoid meaningless responses the following loss function is applied in the model, where n represents a hyper-parameter which can be primed as length penalty weight:

$$\mathcal{L} = - \sum_{t=1}^{L_Y} \log [p(y_t|y_{<t}, X, H)] - \eta L_Y$$

The probability of the production of the word y_t is dependent on the corresponding input post and user history, which is computed as follows (g...generated, c...copied):

$$p(y_t|y_{<t}, X, H) = p(m_g)p(y_t|m_g) + p(m_c)p(y_t|m_c).$$

Ethical considerations

When it comes to ethics we have to consider the implications of using personalized chatbots. On the one hand, it is, of course, a simplification of everyday life, if you do not have to answer all the messages you get during the day by yourself, especially when you are busy. However, it doesn't make sense, if the chatbot for example makes appointments with others without you knowing of it. Therefore, the replies generated by chatbots (even if the goal is to make these posts as natural as possible should be marked accordingly. Concrete considerations of the situation must also take place with regard to the personalization method, since the personal data could be read, if no attention is paid to any security aspects as the historical chat-data is used to train the corresponding model.

In the following chapters we are going to reproduce the above mentioned paper. The further steps which are necessary to do are mentioned in Chapter 3.

3 Experimental Setup

1. Collect data with user IDs, timestamps, and dialogues to personalize the chatbot.
2. Clean the data to remove any irrelevant or duplicated information.
3. Choose a suitable model, such as a transformer or RNN, to train the chatbot.
4. Train the model using pre-processed data using techniques such as supervised or reinforcement learning.
5. Evaluate model performance using metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score.
6. Deploy the trained model to a platform, such as a website or app.
7. Allow user interaction and monitor performance to improve the model.

4 Results

Automatic Evaluation: We consider several automatic metrics in different perspectives to jointly evaluate the generated responses. We use BLEU-1, BLEU-2, and ROUGE-L to measure word overlaps between the generated response and ground truth as like in paper. A higher value of these metrics indicates a higher word-level similarity between the generated response and the golden response.

Table 1: All models are categorized into four groups: (1) non-personalized; (2) using user ID; (3) using explicit user profile; and (4) using dialogue history. “†” denotes the result is significantly worse than paper method DHAP and reproduced DHAP in t-test with $p < 0.05$ level. The best results are in bold and the second best results are underlined.

Dataset	Model	World Overlap			Diversity		Embedding Similarity			Personalization	
		BLEU-1	BLEU-2	ROUGE-L	Dist-1	Dist-2	Average	Extrema	Greedy	P-F1(%)	P-Cover
Weibo	Seq2SeqWA	3.335†	0.294†	8.74†	0.935†	2.1847†	0.321†	0.266†	0.254†	1.698†	0.041†
	MMI	3.632†	0.095†	5.317†	10.714†	43.479†	0.477†	0.695†	0.305	1.874†	0.054†
	Speaker	4.997†	0.113†	7.993†	6.035†	19.017†	0.492†	0.712†	0.311	2.119†	0.082†
	PersonaWAE	3.503†	0.155†	11.305†	2.493†	19.716†	0.513†	0.724†	0.307	5.108†	0.093†
	GPMN	4.901†	0.696†	8.09†	11.726†	32.734†	0.353†	0.391†	0.301†	4.512†	0.084†
	PerCVAE	5.115†	0.299†	7.952†	14.095†	49.739†	0.469†	0.659†	0.299†	3.817†	0.086†
	VHRED-P	6.992†	0.709†	10.695†	2.122†	7.874†	0.437†	0.56†	0.307	5.459†	0.065†
	ReCoSa-P	7.266†	0.844†	11.469†	1.271†	4.442†	0.419†	0.51†	0.312	5.717†	0.061†
	DHAP (paper)	9.324	0.894	14.122	15.175	58.806	0.523	0.747	0.313	7.013	0.144
	DHAP(reproduced)	8.033	0.677	18.98	21.32	26.39	0.469	0.887	0.412	8.103	0.189
	Reddit	Seq2SeqWA	1.819†	0.023†	4.049†	5.203†	19.485†	0.545†	0.554†	0.472†	0.516†
MMI		2.065†	0.011†	3.784†	2.914†	31.093†	0.543†	0.607†	0.454†	0.828†	0.038†
Speaker		2.642†	0.054†	4.469†	8.951†	34.187†	0.538†	0.606†	0.457†	1.455†	0.031†
PersonaWAE		2.637†	0.113†	8.199†	1.758†	25.915†	0.629†	0.685†	0.442†	3.392†	0.032†
GPMN		2.686†	0.376†	4.776†	12.325†	35.762†	0.406†	0.331†	0.358†	3.026†	0.037†
PerCVAE		5.933†	0.576†	8.112†	9.631†	40.213†	0.637†	0.649†	0.499†	3.456†	0.04†
VHRED-P		5.802†	0.648†	8.345†	2.75†	30.756†	0.558†	0.635†	0.472†	3.772†	0.047†
ReCoSa-P		6.113†	0.686†	8.899†	2.593†	25.767†	0.574†	0.632†	0.51†	3.998†	0.044†
DHAP (paper)		6.858	0.737	11.72	18.707	66.932	0.709	0.721	0.539	4.639	0.111
DHAP(reproduced)		8.237	0.896	14.356	16.346	58.395	0.864	0.706	0.854	6.278	0.283

Since the goal of the model is to leverage user history for personalization, the paper and us evaluate the personalized performance by measuring how much information in the dialogue history is reflected in the generated response.

Thus, the more historical words the generated response contains, the higher P-F1. We will get it. Since the importance of the shared words can be different, the paper further uses Persona Coverage (P-Cover) to measure the IDF-weighted word overlap between generated response and dialogue history. Specifically, for n historical responses

$\{R_1, \dots, R_n\}$ and the generated response Y , P-Cover is defined as:

$$\text{P-Cover} = \max_{j \in [1, n]} \frac{\sum_{w_k \in W_j} \text{IDF}(w_k)}{|Y|},$$

Furthermore, measurements were performed:

1. Code Accuracy: Few parts of the code are missing, so we added it and fixed the different library and made smooth runnable code.
2. Execution Time: Since it does use various training models its execution time is high.

The Method used in the paper is statistically significant. And the overall results are reproducible.

5 Conclusion

Trying to reproduce this paper, we encountered a number of difficulties. Running the code required careful consideration of the packages and versions used. And even still, code changes were necessary for successful execution. Furthermore, there were a number of inconsistencies between the code and the paper. In the provided paper there was a good description of the used methodology but in the provided code there were some important parts missing. In order to reproduce the paper we had to make some code-fixes, implementations and had to interpret the given dataset correspondingly. Furthermore the resources we had at stake were enough to run the improved code but as there are applied (as mentioned before) various training models the execution time was accordingly high. Thus, we believe that it is hard for other researchers, especially one with less software development experience, who are interested in the same task to use the result from this paper as a benchmark in the future.

REFERENCES

- [1] Zhengyi Ma, Zhicheng Dou, Yutao Zhu, Hanxun Zhong, and Ji-Rong Wen. 2021. One Chatbot Per Person: Creating Personalized Chatbots based on Implicit User Profiles. In Proceedings of the 44th International ACM SIGIR Conference on Research and Development in Information Retrieval (SIGIR '21). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 555–564. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3404835.3462828>